
Efficacy of Physiotherapy Interventions for Hamstring Tightness among Diverse Population: A Literature Review

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ABSTRACT:

Objective: To explore the effectiveness of various physiotherapy interventions on hamstring tightness.

Methods: Searches were conducted in google scholar, Pubmed, etc. A literature review conducted of only randomized control trial that reported extractable data relevant to the study. The search included all study upto 2015 to 2025. Out of many articles only total of 19 randomized control trial studies were included.

Results: After the segregation process, a total of nine randomized controlled trial (RCT) articles were identified and presented in tabular form. The search process and selection criteria are illustrated in the accompanying flowchart.

Conclusion: Based on the reviewed studies, the most effective physiotherapy interventions for reducing hamstring tightness were found to be combination or advanced techniques, such as Passive Stretching with Quadriceps Activation and the Nordic Hamstring Exercise compared to traditional methods like Static Stretching alone.

KEYWORDS: Hamstring tightness, manual therapy, physiotherapy interventions, stretching.

INTRODUCTION

The hamstring muscle group comprises the semimembranous, semitendinous, and biceps femoris muscles, which commonly originate from the ischial tuberosity. Because of this common muscle origin, contraction of the hamstring muscles results in pelvic posterior tilt as well as hip extension and knee flexion. In addition, because the pelvis is connected to the lumbar spine, pelvic anterior and posterior tilt causes decreased and increased lumbar flexion, to pelvic posterior tilt could cause excessive lumbar flexion.³

The hamstring muscle plays integral role in most leg movements. They are an important muscle group because they balance the actions of the quadriceps muscles and helps in performance of daily activities such as postural adaptations.^{7,2}

Prevalence of hamstring tightness in the general population has been increasing (between 30% and 50%)⁸ and It also appears to be increasing among the youth as it shown in hamstring tightness among undergraduate physical therapy students in Nepal at 40.17%⁵. It has also observed that there is a Decreased hamstring length and low flexibility in elite wrestlers (Callan et al., 2000).⁶

Several factors contribute to hamstring tightness, including age, gender, posture, occupation, muscle strength, endurance, and range of motion. Prolonged sitting, sedentary lifestyle, muscle strain, injury, and poor posture further increase the risk. Decreased muscle control, fatigue, and limited flexibility are common risk factors that lead to reduced mobility and functional performance.⁷

The normal range of hip flexion permitted by the hamstring is in the region of 80 – 90 degrees. Anything less than 80 degree is considered “tight”, Prolonged sitting keeps hamstring in shortened position for a longer period of time which makes it one of the major reasons of reduced hamstring flexibility. Decreased flexibility of a muscle can cause limitation in joint range of motion and muscular imbalance. Reduced hamstring flexibility may lead to hamstring muscle injuries, musculoskeletal disorders like hamstring strains, low back pain, plantar fasciitis and patella femoral pain syndrome and thereby reduces the physical performance of a person.^{7,2}

It is often associated with knee pain, lower extremity injuries, low back pain. It can cause the hip and pelvic to rotate back flattening the lower back and causing lower back problem. It can also be responsible for sacroiliac joint pain, it tends to pull the pelvis out of normal position. Hence Hamstring tightness is an important factor for sports injuries such as hamstring strain which is common among athletes.⁷

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Prevention of hamstring muscle strain requires good hamstring flexibility which can be achieved by various physiotherapeutic techniques like massage therapy, static stretching, dynamic stretching, ballistic stretching, use of foam roller, proprioceptive facilitation

stretching, myofascial released, positional release technique, aerobic and strength training etc.⁷ This study aims to evaluate the impact of physiotherapy stretching interventions and manual therapy techniques on hamstring tightness, providing evidence-based insights that can inform clinical practices and improve patient outcomes. Understanding the efficacy of these stretching interventions will aid in optimizing treatment plans and enhancing the overall management of hamstring tightness.

Need of the study: Hamstring tightness is common due to sedentary habits and poor posture, leading to reduced flexibility and increased injury risk. This study is needed to assess the literature evidence on effectiveness of physiotherapy techniques in improving hamstring flexibility.

Objective of the study: This literature review will specifically examine the existing evidence regarding effectiveness of physiotherapy interventions on hamstring tightness.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Inclusion Criteria

1. This study will include randomized controlled trial publications that specifically investigate the effects of different kinds of physiotherapy interventions on healthy adults with hamstring tightness.
2. Only articles published in the English language will be considered.
3. The articles were published between 2015 and 2025.
4. The age range is from 18 to 60 years.
5. Both sexes are incorporated.

Exclusion Criteria

1. Articles published in languages other than the regional language were omitted.
2. Narrative review, literature other than systematic review articles were excluded.
3. Articles published prior to 2015 were excluded.
4. Studies those are not relevant to the specified keywords.

METHODOLOGY

The evidence for the present study was systematically gathered from reputable online databases and search engines, including Google Scholar and PubMed. A comprehensive search strategy was employed using specific keywords such as “hamstring tightness” and “physiotherapy intervention” to identify relevant scholarly publications. The search was limited to studies published between 2015 and 2025 to ensure the inclusion of recent and highquality evidence from the past decade. Based on the predefined inclusion and exclusion criteria, a total of nine articles were identified as suitable for analysis. All selected studies were obtained in full text and critically reviewed. The extracted data were systematically analysed, and the results have been organised and presented in a tabular format to enhance clarity and facilitate comparative interpretation.

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Flow chart:

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REVIEW OF LITERATURE

AUTHOR (YEAR)	SAMPLE SIZE	AGE GROUP	STUDY DURATION	INTERVENTION	OUTCOME MEASURES	KEY FINDINGS
Yuichi Nishikawa et al.(2015)	54	18-25 yrs	Single session	Active vs Passive Stretching	AKE Test	Both improved flexibility; passive more effective immediately.
Remya N. et al.(2022)	63	18-25 yrs	4 weeks + 1month follow-up	Neurodynamic Sliding, PNF, Static Stretching	AKE, PKE, SLR	All improved; Static better short-term, Neurodynamic better longterm.
Jae-Seop Oh & Min-Hyeok Kang (2021)	24	20-30 yrs	Single session	PNF Hold-Relax vs JackKnife Stretching	AKE, ASLR, FFD	Both improved flexibility; no significant difference.
Faris Alshammari et al.	60	18-24 yrs	1 session	Passive Stretch + Neurodynamic Quadriceps Activation	Goniometer + (Knee Extension ROM)	Quadriceps activation after passive stretch gave greatest improvement.
Robin Vermeulen et al. (2022)	90 male athletes	18-36 yrs	Variable (return-to-sport based)	Early vs Delayed Lengthening Exercises	Return-to-sport time, Reinjury rate	No difference between early and delayed introduction; both effective.
Aydın Balcı et al. (2020)	74 wrestlers	17-19 yrs	1-day intervention	Neural Sliding vs Neural Stretching	AKE, Sit & Reach	Both improved flexibility equally; no superiority.
Hetavi Patel & Deepali Hande (2020)	30 nurses	20-35 yrs	2 weeks	Foam Rolling vs Static Stretching	Sit & Reach, AKE	Foam rolling more effective than static stretching.
Mojtaba Heshmatipour et al.	64 females	18-30 yrs	4 weeks	Active Dynamic vs Passive Static Stretching	AKE	Both improved; active dynamic showed greater effect.
Elham Hosseini et al. (2025)	60 male soccer players	18-25 yrs	8 weeks	Nordic Hamstring Exercise (NHE) vs Dynamic Hamstring Stretching	AKE, Sit & Reach, YBT, Agility, Jump	Both improved flexibility, balance, and agility; NHE superior overall.

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DISCUSSIONS

The aim of this literature review was to gather and categorize papers focused on reducing or treating the hamstring tightness by physiotherapy interventions. We are doing this research to gain more exposure of what more techniques are there related to physiotherapy to treat hamstring tightness .

We have found many articles in a variety of reputable journals that correspond to our keywords. After examining the inclusion and exclusion criteria, we were able to gather

9 articles in the form of randomized controlled trials (RCTs) from the years 2015 to 2025. There are other articles also with interventions like cupping, dry needling for this condition but here we are focusing on physiotherapy interventions only.

These articles will be further analysed. Randomized controlled trials (RCTs) were selected due to their inclusion of exercise protocols and the author's perspectives or findings, as compared to review articles.

All 9 articles had a distinct outcome measures to confirm diagnosis and all interventions routine tailored to fit the individual needs were there in their respective test groups.

After analysing 9 papers, we discovered that all of them shown a beneficial impact. Furthermore, the impact is optimized when participants receive a combination intervention rather than a single intervention.

The research duration ranged from 3 weeks to 1 year, which is considered sufficient for reducing hamstring tightness. It is evident that a longer training period would yield even better results for the participants

The prevalent outcome measures consisted of Active knee extension (AKE) , Passive knee extension (PKE), Straight leg raise (SLR) , Hip flexion ROM ,Active straight leg raise (ASLR) , Finger to floor distance (FFD), knee extension ROM, return to sport time , reinjury rate, sit and reach test , Y balance test (YBT) , agility and jump.

Physiotherapy interventions were used like active stretching , passive stretching , dynamic stretching , neurodynamic slidings , PNF stretching , static stretching , PNF hold-relax , jack knife stretching , quadriceps activation , delayed lengthening exercises , neural sliding , neural stretching , Nordic hamstring exercises.

yuichi nishikawa et al. (2015) conducted a study titled “immediate effect of passive and active stretching on hamstrings flexibility: a single-blinded randomized control trial.” the trial involved 54 healthy young adults who were randomly assigned into three groups — active stretching, passive stretching, and control. the intervention aimed to compare the effectiveness of passive versus active stretching techniques in improving hamstring flexibility. the study measured outcomes using the active knee extension test (aket) before and immediately after stretching. findings revealed that both stretching techniques significantly improved hamstring flexibility compared to the control group; however, passive stretching showed greater improvement than active stretching.

Remya N. et al. (2022) conducted a study titled “Comparison of Immediate and Long Term Effects of Neurodynamic Sliding, PNF Stretching and Static Stretching on Hamstring Flexibility in Young Adults with Hamstring Tightness.” The study included 63 subjects

(aged 18–25 years) divided into three groups: Neurodynamic Sliding, PNF Stretching, and Static Stretching. The intervention was administered 3 times per week for 4 weeks, and outcomes were measured using Active Knee Extension (AKE), Passive Knee Extension (PKE), and Straight Leg Raise (SLR) tests. The results revealed that all interventions significantly improved hamstring flexibility, with Static Stretching showing greater immediate effects, while Neurodynamic Sliding demonstrated better long-term improvement.

Jae-Seop Oh and Min-Hyeok Kang (2021) conducted a study titled “The Effectiveness of Hamstring Stretching with Proprioceptive Neuromuscular Facilitation versus Jack-Knife Stretching for Individuals with Hamstring Tightness.” The randomized controlled clinical trial included 24 adults with bilateral hamstring tightness who were assigned to either the PNF Stretching group or Jack-Knife Stretching group. Each participant performed 150 seconds of stretching, and outcomes were assessed using Active Knee Extension (AKE), Active Straight Leg Raise (ASLR), and Finger-to-Floor Distance (FFD) tests. Both interventions significantly increased hamstring flexibility and improved pelvic and lumbar movement, with no significant difference between the two groups.

A study conducted by Alshammari F. et al. in 2019 was A novel approach to improve hamstring flexibility: A single-blinded randomised clinical trial. The trial included 60 participants aged

18–24 with shortened hamstrings. The involved interventions compared three groups: Passive Hamstring Stretch (PS) only, PS followed by a Tibial Nerve Neurodynamic Technique (ND), and PS followed by Active Knee Extension–Quadriceps Activation (QA).The conclusion was that quadriceps activation following passive hamstring stretching can be used in physiotherapy settings to improve hamstring muscle flexibility.

A study conducted by Vermeulen R et.al in 2022 was the Early versus delayed lengthening exercises for acute hamstring injury in male athletes: a randomised controlled clinical trial. The trial involved 90 male athletes with an acute hamstring injury. The involved interventions were a comparison of introducing lengthening (eccentric strengthening) exercises at two time points: Early (day 1 of

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rehabilitation) vs. Delayed (after running at 70% max speed), with both groups receiving an established rehabilitation programme. The main outcomes measured were time to

Return to Sport (RTS) and reinjury rate at 12 months. Accelerating the introduction of lengthening exercises did not improve the time to Return to Sport (median RTS 23 days vs 33 days, $p=0.84$) nor the risk of reinjury.

A study conducted by Balci A et.al in 2020 was the The effect of different neural mobilization exercises on hamstring flexibility and functional flexibility in wrestlers. The trial was a shortterm study (single session). The involved interventions were Sciatic nerve neural sliding exercises vs. Sciatic nerve neural stretching exercises. The outcomes measured were hamstring flexibility (Active Knee Extension Limitation/AKEL angle) and functional flexibility (Sit and Reach/SR test). Both neural sliding and neural stretching exercises were equally effective in producing significant short-term increases in hamstring flexibility and functional flexibility from pre- to post-mobilization, with neither technique being superior to the other.

A study conducted by Patel H G et.al in 2020 was the “Effect of foam rolling versus static stretching on hamstring tightness in nurses”. The trial compared pre- and post-intervention results. The involved interventions were Foam Rolling vs. Static Stretching. The outcomes measured were hamstring tightness (Sit and Reach test and Active Knee Extension test). Both Foam Rolling and Static Stretching showed a significant improvement in hamstring tightness. But Foam Rolling was found to be more effective than Static Stretching for improving hamstring tightness.

A study conducted by Heshmatipour M et.al in 2019 was the Effect of Active Dynamic Versus Passive Static Stretching on Hamstring Muscle Tightness in Healthy Female Students: A Randomized Trial Study. The trial lasted for 4 weeks (5 days per week). The involved interventions were Active Dynamic Stretching vs. Passive Static Stretching. The main outcome measured was Active Knee Extension range of motion (ROM). Both active dynamic stretching and passive static stretching led to significant improvements in hamstring flexibility. But Active Dynamic Stretching showed better results and a greater effect on ROM compared to passive static stretching.

A study conducted by Hosseini E et.al in 2025 was the The effects of 8 weeks of dynamic hamstring stretching or nordic hamstring exercises on balance, range of motion, agility, and muscle performance among male soccer players with hamstring shortness: a randomized controlled trial. The trial lasted for 8 weeks. The involved interventions were Nordic Hamstring Exercises (NHE), Dynamic Hamstring Stretching (DHS), and a Control (CO) group. The outcomes measured included Range of Motion (ROM), balance (YBT), agility (IAT), and muscle performance (CMJ). Both NHE and DHS significantly improved ROM, balance, agility, and muscle performance. But Nordic Hamstring Exercises (NHE) demonstrated superior effects compared to Dynamic Hamstring Stretching (DHS) in all measured parameters (except CMJ)

LIMITATION AND RECOMMENDATION

A key limitation is the absence of occupational stratification; the study provided a general overview across professions but failed to examine outcomes specific to different occupational groups. Future researchers can utilize this article for intervention regarding for hamstring tightness and they can conduct RCTs and systematic reviews in future.

CONCLUSION

Based on this literature review, there are various physiotherapy techniques utilized as effective interventions to improve hamstring flexibility. All included data indicated improvements in flexibility across nearly all intervention groups. However, the results suggest the effect size is more prominent in combination or advanced interventions (such as Passive Stretch + Quadriceps Activation or Nordic Hamstring Exercise) compared to single or traditional methods (like Static Stretching alone). We suggest conducting additional studies on this topic, such as Systematic Reviews or Randomized Controlled Trials focusing on quantifying the long-term superiority of combination therapies implemented by different researchers

ABBREVIATION

- RCT- Randomised control trial • AKE -Active knee extension
- PKE -Passive knee extension
- SLR- Straight leg
- ASLR -Active straight leg raise
- FFD -finger to floor distance
- YBT -Y balance test
- ROM- range of motion

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